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OXIDATION AND INDENTATION RESISTANCE OF CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITE BY SILICON CARBIDE COATING

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Introduction, Evaluation method-oxidation test

- Carbon-carbon composite is desirable for candidate materials of heat insulation and high temperature heater. However, the disadvantage of carbon-carbon composite is low oxidation resistance at high temperature and lower wear resistance. Therefore, this study investigates oxidation and indentation resistance of C_f -C composites to evaluate oxidation indentation resistance.
- We perform the oxidation tests by thermal cycling on the composites without coating and SiC coated C_f -C composites at different temperatures, 500, 1000, 1350 and 1500°C. The maximum cycles were performed in air if no cracks or interface delamination occurs. The cycles was stopped if cracks or interface delamination occurs. We measured and compared the weight change of each cycle.

Evaluation – indentation test

- The Hertzian indentation test was carried out to evaluate the indentation resistance of SiC coated composite and the composite without coating. We used a WC spherical indenter with a radius of $r = 3.18\text{mm}$, and the load was increased to certain load and unload using universal testing machine. The indentation load and displacement curves were compared to each other. All tests were conducted in air.

Main result – oxidation test

- The oxidation tests show that the SiC coating is beneficial to reduce of weight loss during thermal cycling oxidation test.

Main result – indentation test

- The indentation tests show that the SiC coating is beneficial to improve the elastic property of C_f-C composite.

Main result – burner test

- The burner tests at 1700 ~ 2000°C show that the SiC coating is beneficial to protect the C_f-C composite from high temperature.

